

Pinagpala Publishing Services

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

VOL.V ISSUE XI

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

November 2025
Monthly Issue
International

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269
DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433
TIN 293-150-678/ Business Permit No. 8183
San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300
pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
+639684666397

*"Write. Educate.
Connect."*

Q @pinagpalapublishingservices

Q pinagpala_publishing

Q www.pinagpalapublishing.com

to be
point of
Teach [ti
impart
guide in
duca

**LEADERSHIP
=
RESULTS**

World Education Connect Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume V, Issue XI (November 2025), p.76, International

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678/ Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

STRENGTHENING TEACHERS' SUBJECT-MATTER EXPERTISE

Jewelston M. Santos, PhD¹ Glen B. Millar, MAEd² Jovi Jane C. Bernales, PhD³

Assistant Professor IV, University of Batangas – Lipa City¹

Assistant Professor IV, University of Batangas – Lipa City²

Associate Professor I, University of Batangas – Lipa City³

The Teacher Education Council (TEC) sheds light on the continuing trend in graduate studies being taken by teachers in the Department of Education (DepEd). Based on the School Form 7 (SF7) data, the majority of teachers enrolled in graduate programs are leaning more toward educational leadership rather than acquiring advanced studies in core disciplines such as English, Math, or Science.

To illustrate, 15,956 educational leaders hold master's degrees which is a stark contrast to the 11,557 who specialized in English, 9,177 in Math, and 5,612 in Science. Furthermore, there is also a mismatch at the doctorate level as well, 1,276 educational leaders hold doctorates, in comparison to 1,064 in English, 692 in Math, and 494 in Science. This shows that a significant gap exists between administrative and educational subject matter focused on graduate studies.

The trend also begs the question on the true focus of graduate studies in education. Although leadership and management are pillars of educational administration, there is no clear link in their impact to teaching and learning outcomes. It is clear that leadership programs, as the TEC stressed, will not help teachers master their own subject which an essential factor in delivering quality education.

An imbalanced focus on teachers' instructional work and their leadership constructions results from how promotion incentives work in education. Many teachers believe leadership degrees confer a competitive edge in their career and take these rather than subject specific degrees. When this occurs, the perception of professional advancement holds that it will involve stepping out of the teaching practice instead of refining it. This unnecessary perception deflection from the teaching practice, influence most on the learning of the students, causes a significant opportunity cost.

To remediate this, schools and departments of education should ensure that faculty are not promoting scholarship for the sake of scholarship. Research, and innovative and fusion pedagogy should inform curriculum revision and fusion pedagogy for subject disciplines, along with scholarship in education disciplines. Informed curriculum and instruction will encourage mastery and relevance integration focus. Meanwhile, it is high time that DepEd and education policymakers come up with incentives and disincentives that will focus on teacher's degrees that are aligned with teaching and learning high outcomes instead of degrees that lean teaching and instructional administration.

Placing graduate education back toward the classroom is not just a reformative measure; it is a necessity. Graduate education ought to be aimed at building the construction of outstanding teaching—educators who not only lead but who inspire with profound content knowledge and skilled teaching. To achieve this, the education system ought to ensure that professional recognition and impact in the classroom advance simultaneously.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17614062

Copyright © 2025 by Pinagpala Publishing Services

Indexed at Google Scholar, Zonodo, OpenAire, Philippine eJournals, Google, Yahoo, MS Bing